

Articles for the Ancient Kentucke Historical Association

By Sf. Ramon Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM, L.Ac.

Article best viewed at: <https://bit.ly/3h1ztBe>

Kithiki Dreaming

by Shifu Ramon Careaga

In an attempt to give the reader some understanding of the scope of the “Hidden Destinations in KY” project, we’ve decided to have a monthly column of newest researches. Of course this is already five years into the project, and many of the most commonly known things have been achieved. Yet, new things keep coming out of the woodwork, so to speak. Check out this video displaying the [Fall Branch Falls](https://goo.gl/zmy6C8) (goo.gl/zmy6C8) and the next one, [Ruin Falls](https://goo.gl/y31VQQ) (<https://goo.gl/y31VQQ>). These two waterfalls are located east of the Daniel Boone National Forest and receive no state protection whatsoever.

Also, I found in Perryville, this cave (right). Doesn’t seem like a big deal until you read the sign accompanying it. I’ll let you google “Perryville Cave,” or [read the sign here: https://goo.gl/zZ9X4o](https://goo.gl/zZ9X4o)

Note that the cave used to be big enough to enter, and its stream still flows and dumps out into the Chapman River. All of this you can visit when you go to Perryville Battlefield Monument and visit “Merchant’s Row.”

A lot of lost history is contained in these off-center regions of mid-eastern and mid-western Kentucky.

The point being, if the state won’t market it, the only way you will see these things is to go and stop yourself. I have passed this stretch of US 68 dozens of times, and there is no indicator that there is a historically important cave visible from the road. Only by visiting Merchant’s Row itself could this be discerned. Perryville was the highlight of that day’s trip. I make dozens of trips a year. Last weekend was Carter Caves and Louisa. What I learned in Louisa at the Fred E Vinson Museum blew me away. This man is not only Kentucky’s only Supreme court Chief Justice, but he was also one of two people to serve all three branches and the UN, and is the man most chiefly responsible for making the dollar the world’s standard and establishing the IMF and World Bank. He was a great man. He grew up in a house attached to the jail, as his father was the Sheriff. But remarkable to me also was the stonework on this jail still available to see. Large, practically megalithic, and from far away near to Morehead, they simply don’t build things this sturdy, anymore. No state funding. Private grants only.

Ultimately my point is that Kithiki/ Kentucke/ Caintuck can be viewed on multiple levels **and we should insist upon it**. There is the ancient

foregone “Avatar”esque period, the antiquity of the mound builders and their wild world of large trees,

hidden earthworks of “the gods,” and springs, caves, falls, and arches that dotted the land leaving a realm of wonder. After that, the historical periods which are Pre-English, Pioneer, Antebellum, Post-bellum, and finally the modern industrialized Kentucky. Within each are history “shells” that are easily forgotten if we as the public do not learn them and pass on to the youth these historical marvels. I have found hundreds of such examples. It’s why I continue my work, and to build upon the map (hiddendestinationsky.com) and the book. It won’t be long before stay-cationing in Kentucky is really, “a dream come true.”

Monday Night Live on Facebook

by Shifu Ramon Careaga

Two videos of interest have occurred on member “Medium Kathryn Kauffman’s” channel on youtube. One was a follow-up to Chris Dunn and Eric Wilson’s spectacular presentation at the February meeting. Entitled “[Giza Power Plant and Atlantis theory](https://goo.gl/qnqCbg)” (<https://goo.gl/qnqCbg>) this chat explored the Extended Plasma-Electromagnetic Universe model ([white paper available here: https://goo.gl/tqZKSh](https://goo.gl/tqZKSh)) understanding of how and where all of these unique alternate cosmologies can fit in together with a simplified narrative, backed by electromagnetic science and plasma petroglyph evidence (as well as mythological evidence).

The second video was more in line with the “goals” of Ancient Kentucke Historical Association, that is the exploration of the “King Arthur Conspiracy” especially as it relates to King Arthur and the Welsh/Khumry people being in the Ohio River Valley area. Entitled, “[The King Arthur Conspiracy and Welsh Indians in KY](https://goo.gl/qiW4bj)” (<https://goo.gl/qiW4bj>), member Shifu Careaga attempts to briefly explain the Wilson/Blacket/Michael/Pennington hypothesis to catch Kathryn’s native Kentuckian and national audience up on the hidden, indeed “bondaged” history of Wales as envisioned by stele evidence and Alan Wilson et al...

Shifu Careaga joins Madame Kathryn every month on Facebook “Monday Night Live” on the third or fourth Monday of the month at 7pm. The next episode will be a hard return to the science of the Electric Universe for an important up-review of the sciences.

Shifu Careaga explains electrically driven crustal collapse theory, credit: Robert Distinti (<https://www.youtube.com/user/rdistinti>)

So much has happened lately to support the non-mainstream narratives that it requires its own episode!

History Consumed is History Forgotten

by Sf. Ramon Careaga

I am generally unable to wait forever for my research. Or in this case, it doesn't wait for me. As some of you know I am going to organize a trip for dogfoot hollow to research potential stone fortification and artifacts near to Berea. However, in the meantime, KYWilderness.com hosted a **long** hike out at Red River Gorge - in the Clifty Wilderness - to Castle and Red Byrd Arches. My school brought about six people. It turned from a seven mile trek to an eleven

mile adventure. Aside from the natural beauty, it was very intriguing to find the remains of an old homestead and a well (and the “wild” daffodils left behind) deep in those protected woods. Now, consider, based on this photo of a hearth how old this home could be. Certainly no more than 200 years. It is difficult to find good historical records for these unaddressed homes.

But look at the forest's progress in consuming the property. Consider, additionally, the depth that [Troy](#) was found at: perhaps up to 20 feet or more? It is therefore, my assertion that when it comes to researching pre-Columbian settlements, such as those found off the [gulf coast of Florida at Manasota Key](#) (which may be as old as 7000 BCE), we have to consider a couple factors. One is the wet nature of Ohio

River Valley and the large amount of flood plains, rivers, drainages, and high amounts of erosion. It very well could be that we will find even more settlements, or even fortifications if there is a deep earth penetrating study performed!

Consider this “Adena” structure at “Adena Meadows” in the forest in the Gorge:

How unfortunate that this site is not protected or discussed at the Red River Gorge. It is easily seen with the new LiDAR release “KY From Above” that came out just this year (2018). It is a complex earthwork, possibly a village structure, but given the typical Allegewi behavior of living away from earthworks, it can be assumed to be either symbolic, religious, or astronomically related. I will continue to search out for archaeological studies, however, from what I have seen,

even when a site is moderately known, such as the Russellville Lost City or the Boyd Serpent Mound or Spratt Mound and earthworks, the state and University studies are not thoroughly encompassing to form anywhere near a rigorously testable hypothesis. Certainly wherever Ohio archaeology is at, concerning earthworks and serpent mounds, KY is far, far behind in: data, sampling, testing, analysis, preservation, and public education. This gives leeway for alternate or diffusionist, typically amateur archaeological exploration, but it also provides a way for the powers that be to buffer against resistance to preset (untested) ideas, and theories that have more holes than Swiss cheese.

Boyd Stone Serpent Mound

It keeps the public ignorant as well of the historical, cultural, and potentially genealogical heritage, and this seems a mighty disservice to the Commonwealth; be they of native descent or otherwise. It's my contention that we should investigate using this LiDAR data and see what else is "hiding underfoot." It might be that we are one step closer to revealing the lost secrets of the Allegewi, be they Welsh, Viking, Roman, or American Indian.

Lost City of Russellville area - away from mounds.

Panoramic shot from last month's meeting, featuring Chris Dunn & Eric Wilson

"Kentucky From Above" and Website News

Kentucky From Above has finally completed and released the most up to date 5 foot DEM LiDAR (Light/Laser Detection and Ranging). Links to KY From Above are up on our website, www.ancientkentucke.com where Sf. Ramon is working on embedding it. There are a number of ways to process this data, for example use in CalTopo or ArcGIS). Although the main online viewing platform remains fairly difficult to use for non-experts, a simple, color version can be found by opening <http://kygeonet.ky.gov/StoryMaps/KyFromAboveElevation/> and selecting #9 and zooming out. You should be able to drive the map anywhere in the state and use the same settings. If there are any questions please contact me (Ramon) via email or visit KY From Above's website.

NOTE TO ALL MEMBERS - You may receive access to the Members Only section of the website, found at www.akha.us with any gmail account. Simply send an email to ramon@bluelotushealth.com from your GMAIL address and you can be added. Unfortunately, only gmail users can access due to limitations from Google Sites. Also, please perform your renewals easily, and quickly online from the Memberships page (purchase with Paypal and submit online): <https://sites.google.com/site/ancientky/home/membership> Thank you! ~Sf. Ramon Careaga

Right Under Our Noses

by Sf. Ramon Careaga

I am known - these days - for my exotic travels within the state. Or outside. I just returned with kids in tow from visiting Cahokia and the Missouri Botanical Gardens, both of which are assuredly top notch gems in the whole of the United States. The gardens, in particular blew my mind. But running up Monk's Mound with my daughter on my back as well as a thunderstorm threatening behind sure was memorable!

However, on occasion this state throws me a 'curve ball' when I least expect it, and least look for it. I have had two such curve balls this past month. The first, came at me for a couple reasons. Chiefly, it was because I generally expect on a *good day* of research to unveil an A+ or A++ scored location, but only once that day. It is highly unlikely to see several in a single day (see table 2). Yet, that is precisely what happened on my journey south in late May. Taking in the whole of the Barren River Lake area, I have to say everything, from the drive on KY-100 (which absolutely should be on your fall drive plans), to finding and cataloguing the "hot tip" of the Dry Fork Gorge preserve

was already *top notch*. But on a day when I find not only salamanders¹ and working historic sulphur well springs, to find also *two* breathtaking waterfalls (Dry Fork cave+falls, and Brushy Creek Church Falls, the latter of which was a stunning limestone spring with plenty of negative ions to peel away the stress), a historic courthouse and log home, bypass two preserves and **still** wind up at a place like Clay Hill Memorial Forest, which scored a 100% A++ is extremely rare.² To put it in perspective, only one other preserve has managed to score a 100% and that was only because it was attached to Shaker village

and had facilities. Every other 100% score in KY has come from non-preserves.³

AVG Score: ⁴	86.13615023	B+, Silver
# entries	639	

I cannot easily express the sheer joy of walking in true Kentucky woods, without having to travel far to Blanton or climb difficult hills like at Lilley Cornett, or to have to swat at migs like at Wyatt Jeffries. Clay Hill is truly, an honest to God hidden gem in this state.

So what would you think, then, if I were to say that despite such a success, a place like Raven's Run SNP in Lexington still holds surprises? If you're familiar with the photography of onemansadventure, or with his waterfall database map, you will note that there's only one falls shown at Raven's Run. I knew of two. The second

¹ Top: Upper Raven's Run branch; Right: KY Spotted-tail Salamander, Dry Fork Gorge, Southern KY

² Top-left: Figure 1 from my Tourism Ranking Data, latest values

³ Right: Brush Creek Baptist Church Falls

⁴ Table 1: Average scores throughout KY. 86% is the cut-off from Bronze to Silver

of which is the **actual** tallest in the state⁵. But to discover via mere curiosity and wayfaring that a preserve I had visited dozens of times (being in my hometown) since I was a small boy held two more waterfalls... well it was humbling.⁶

Hiestand House/ Taylor Co History Museum ⁷	99	A++,Crème de la Crème
Skyline Drivein Theatre	99	A++,Crème de la Crème
Green Co Historic Courthouse and square	99	A++,Crème de la Crème
Tebb's Bend Battle Driving Tour and Trail	99	A++,Crème de la Crème
First Creek, Mammoth Cave NP	85	B, Bronze
Port Oliver Rec Area/Bike Trails	93	A-,Gold
Quarry Rd Rec Area (Barren River Lake)	92	A-,Gold
Tailwater Rec Area (Green River Lake)	97	A+, Best of the Best
Sky View Drive In Theatre	69	D, Endangered
Brush Creek Church Falls	95	A,Top Honors
Sulphur Well Historic Park	99	A++,Crème de la Crème
Dry Fork Gorge	92	A-,Gold
Clay Hill Memorial Forest	100	A++,Crème de la Crème
Missy's Out of the Way Cafe	93	A-,Gold
Anderson County History Museum	93	A-,Gold

How much can exist *right under our noses* without us seeing it? I feel that there is something to my theory of “reality mining” and indeed, in this case, “Reality plowing.” The more I drive and hike, the more the state gives back to me. It beckons, “Let me show you more.” I came home from that hike and found 10 new destinations around the KY River Palisades⁸ to add to the map (thereby extending my project!) After Cahokia and the drive back I found Chris (onemansadventure) had posted a half dozen more waterfalls in northern KY!

The mysteries unfold for me, at an advancing rate... I hope you will take up the call to seek them as well. Kentucky is waking up.

⁵ ~160’ cascade; Yahoo Falls is 112’

⁶ Top-right: High canopy near “Little Angel Spring”, where a tomb lies in quietude.

⁷ Table 2: Selection from data, Barren River Lake trip, 5-25-2018

⁸ Bottom-left: Kentucky River Palisades subregion (of the Bluegrass); did you know that the riverbed is the second oldest river bedrock in the world? (~450 million years old), but the river is only a few million years old as far as we know.

Hidden Destinations: lost roads of Daniel Boone National Forest

by Sf. Ramon Careaga

The roads through the Daniel Boone⁹, and the trails that form on roads that are no longer serviced, tell an American tale. That tale *feels* like the TVA and Army Corps era, when exploration of the country was at its height, and trails were laid for generations to come.

Walking in these road-trails in the Daniel Boone is often a brushy business. I've returned from such a weekend in the Big South Fork National Recreational Area, cut up on the legs, feeling the simultaneous exhilaration of finding lost or hidden arches and waterfalls (many of which you can swim in, see right: Little Rock Creek Preserve), and the sadness that the state and federal government has so neglected so many of these marvels, in favor of funding only the most popular and reachable.

The consequence of this policy is that (aside from a tender box) the best features, many of which

are historic from the pioneer, Indian, and antebellum periods of Kentucky/Ohio River Valley history are left to be forgotten by an increasingly sedentary society. Though it's true, brambles don't call to everyone, what touches my heart is the hidden history. Why do they call it "Robber's Roost Arch?" Why is it called "Princess Falls?" Is there a story there, from either the coal mining era (Stearns was a huge hub of coal mining, and to this day the Big South Fork Scenic Railway & Museum remains probably the best of the lot in KY to visit) or from

⁹ Top: Marcus Falls, Daniel Boone National Forest Bottom: rhododendron blooms at Claw Arch, off the road.

pioneer days? I have read that at Yahoo (Ywahoo) Falls there was a terrible massacre of Cherokee women and children, and the ominous glyph “kill” is all that remains there to tell the tale.¹⁰ But the park has no information on site.

Hollow Rock Arch, Big South Fork

My goal, if I had one ‘aside’ goal of many in this project, would be to get enough people hiking and traveling (even by 4x4) on these lost and lonely roads - many which have nary a single person to encounter in a whole afternoon of sojourn - to be able to realistically lobby the government to reopen them. Perhaps a resurgence of popularity in driving trails could encourage hiking and better forest management. It would certainly save the Red and Natural Bridge State Park from being “loved to death,” if more places throughout the 300 mile forest were explored. My recommendation, if you try, is to go to hiddendestinationsky.com and use the feature on the map “Daniel Boone Parkway” which I have designed for just such a staycation. It can take a long weekend, but there is **plenty** to see.

Dick Gap Scenic Overlook, Big South Fork of the Cumberland River

(center left is the Mining Town, part of BSF Railroad tour; center right is “Devil’s Jump Rapids”)

Atlantologists may enjoy...

[“Unboxing Atlantis,” by Sf. Ramon Careaga.](#)

Now available on the [Electric Universe Gateway](#)

¹⁰ <https://ourtexasfamilycom.ipage.com/BrockWebSite/YahooFalls-byKTankersley.html>

Note: the entire EPEMC paper set is a work in progress, and it may be handy to consult previous or later papers to understand the [HEGEME mechanisms](#) set forth in the above paper.

Hidden Geology Revelations in Kentucky

By Sf. Ramon Careaga

Huffing and puffing my way up to the top of Cumberland Mountain, one of the largest and most visually impressive in Kentucky, I was reminded of how *difficult* it would be for the pioneers to - with lack of the power of hindsight and technology we now have - know exactly what to expect. The White Rocks are formidable, and the sides of Stone/Cumberland Mountain seem indomitable, especially for wagons. Yet, the Gap and the Wilderness Road/Warrior's Path that follow the wide Buffalo Traces up into the interior of Caintuck must have been so inviting.

(Above: White Rocks, Cumberland Gap NHP)¹¹

What would they find? What type of Avatar's Pandora-esque place lay behind the Cumberland? A land of arches, massive trees, sulphur spring wells, natural gas fire-vents, caves and rock shelters. And to add more to the mystery: a land of mounds, earthworks, tombs, mummies¹², and pyramids.

Can you imagine the excitement?

I happen to experience this excitement regularly (albeit in far less quantity than Daniel Boone) through my project, the [Hidden Destinations in Kentucky map](#) (www.hiddendestinationsky.com) and forthcoming book. I will be presenting upon this subject in November's meeting. The sheer joy of uncovering not truly *lost* places (except a few places I go¹³) but so much as *lost to cultural consciousness* places, is indescribable. People simply do not know what is in our state. Places like Angel Hollow, Wind Cave, Little Egypt, Horse Lick Bioreserve, and Blood River Seeps

¹¹ <http://www.cumberlandgapregion.com/hiking-trails/>

¹² "History of Lexington, Kentucky" G Ranck, 1872, <https://archive.org/details/cu31924028845993>

¹³ Lost Arch literally has no forest road to it anymore.

beckon me. When I hear about a new place I get excited all over again to encounter the real Kentucky. Not that there's anything wrong with horses, bourbon and basketball. But there's just simply so much more.

Even five years into the project I still get surprised. As I mentioned, the state released the last section of the Kentucky From Above LiDAR map. So I've begun, in earnest, searching for the remainder of said mounds and pyramids¹⁴, earthworks and forts. I just happened to be looking in the Versailles area for a mound complex when my eyes moved across the "Big Sink Astrobleme."

Middlesboro Crater oblique strike¹⁵

Jephtha Knob oblique strike¹⁶

I have already been to and photographed this location, but... well see for yourself! It's neither a sink, nor an astrobleme. It is very clearly a result of the Thunderbolt arc discharge the Indians mentioned to Thomas Jefferson¹⁷. It wasn't a very long-held strike location, perhaps only

¹⁴ Above: Butterfield Mound Complex (Woodland Era) is known, but the pyramid has a historic cemetery on top of it, which means it has never been opened up, and is not generally mentioned. Another LiDAR discovery.

¹⁵ All of these are taken with KY From Above LiDAR scans.

¹⁶ Compare with Big Sink below: no bow shock, no clear vector in or outblast center and out + clear signs of electric arc discharge sputtering, scalloping (albeit eroded), and crater chaining (and vector change)

¹⁷ "A [Delaware] Chief in the group stood up and said, 'In ancient times a herd of these tremendous animals came to the Big Bone Licks, and began a universal destruction of the bear, deer, elks, buffaloes, and other animals which had been created for the use of the Indians; that **the Great Man above, looking down and seeing this, was so enraged that he seized his lightning, descended on the Earth, seated himself on a neighboring mountain, on a rock of which his seat and the print of his feet, and hurled his bolts among them till the whole were slaughtered**, except the big bull who, presenting his forehead to the shafts, shook them off as they fell; but missing one at length, it wounded him in the side; whereon, springing round, he bounded over the Ohio, over the Wabash, the Illinois, and finally over the great lakes, where he is living at this day.'"

a single blast of tenths of a second to seconds.

There is a clear difference. This is an archetypal conical mound formation; with enough time it can be raised higher or form fulguritic basalt formations. It is 1640m (5,421' or over 1 mile) in diameter. I am not sure what the power level of such a strike would be, but a single lightning bolt is about 5 billion joules. So it'd be probably on the order of a billion billion or more. It's a stupendous find, and one that is going into my paper, "Plasma Petroglyphs and Geoglyphs."¹⁸

(right: Birkeland Current Thunderbolt, credit: Dr. Anthony Peratt, Los Alamos Labs)

~In Search of Ice Age Americans, Tankersley, p.51-52

¹⁸ Bear in mind, as well, that within EPEMC hypothesis, the proximity of this strike to the Allegewi earthworks in Lexington is not a coincidence (just as Great Serpent Mound being on another inexplicable "astrobleme" isn't). This would have been religiously significant, as would the C-henge strike at Mt. Horeb. Were the events seen by humans? Or found by humans later? Certainly anything within a large radius would have died almost instantly if not up in a tree or in a cave. More research needs to be done.

<https://geosurvey.ohiodnr.gov/portals/geosurvey/PDFs/newsletter/Winter94.pdf>

Like I've said before, with Kentucky, "You don't know till you go." But in this case, I went. So the study of some of these fantastic geologies is going to take a lot more analysis. All these years after Daniel Boone, and still what do we know about the land, really? I hope some of you have been to Kentucky's Old Growth forests, because it really is a different experience (especially Clay Hill Memorial Forest). But when you go, try to place your mind back in time to the Archaic/Paleo period, and to when there were giant things in the land. What would the New World have been like (for all its beauty and inhospitability) for the Welsh, Vikings, Romans, and Spanish when they first arrived? What would it have been like for the civilizing cultures of the Allegewi, Hopewell, Cahokians, Toltec, Anasazi etc... surrounded by mortal enemies that

despised fortifications? When they made their mounds after the constellations (places like Aztalan, Shiloh, and Poverty Point), what did they see? It's exotic, it's remote, it's understudied. It is, to me, just like Avatar. Only more gas stations and fast food stops and no dire wolves or short-faced bears.

(Left: Conical hill formed by lightning; credit: Andy Hall)

Vanishing or Unique Kentucky Architecture

By Sf. Ramon Careaga

As many of you are aware, there are few examples of megalithic work in Kentucky, and even fewer remaining. I've come across stones weighing a few tons, and of course iron furnaces with plenty of heavy stone. There are bridgeworks, and stone forts, walls and the like. But this is not the only kind of lost architecture we have in Kentucky. Broadly speaking I would divide the lost architecture into five categories: (1) historic buildings and forts, (2) Native earthworks, (3) mysterious stone forts and walls, (4) Dams, mills, and bridges, especially of note, (5) special and underappreciated marvels left to rot.

While Louisville has done a decent job of late in restoring and retaining Victorian mansions in the country's largest Victorian preserve (Historic Old Louisville), it has, of course let go some architectural marvels you may not have been aware of. Prior to the building of several of the homes there, for example, there was the world's largest wooden structure (45 acres), the *Southern Exposition*, from 1883-1887. It was always meant to be temporary, but imagine the amazing marvel of seeing not only a building so large, but one lit by the fantastic new invention: the electric light bulb!

Southern Exposition, 1883; Credit: Wikipedia Commons

Speaking of lost marvels, KY has scant remaining historic covered bridges¹⁹ (13); some of which are still driveable²⁰. But did you know that US-27 was once home to a 240' two-lane

¹⁹ <https://www.coveredbridgemap.com/ky/>

²⁰ <http://www.dalejtravis.com/cblist/cbky.htm>

covered bridge that spanned the Kentucky River (1838-1933)²¹? And that Kentucky once had the world's longest wooden covered bridge (Butler Station Bridge 456')²², which was destroyed by arson²³. To this day Kentucky has some of the most unique examples of truss structure in the country.

Speaking of the KY River, many people know of the tributary, the Dix River. Many more people are aware of Herington Reservoir. But, because the dam remains out of normal view, few people are aware of the architectural wonder that is Dix Dam, at one time (1925) the tallest dam of its kind, in the world (287', 87m)²⁴. Goddard Bridge, last lattice-truss in KY²⁵

Middle-left: Dix Dam

Upper-right:

leakage. Nor is there a sign or a plaque for it. I featured this dam on the group's facebook cover, recently, but here (bottom-right) is an image of it with the original country club, now gone.

As for lost, or burnt buildings, there are many numerous examples of destroyed springs hotels, such as Drennon, Sulphur Well, Bee Rock, and of course

Near to Louisville, the Sleepy Hollow Dam remains alone as a symbol of a bygone era of gaiety, and country club fanfare, in an era when carnivals, theme parks, and fairs littered the country with bemusing entertainment and revelry. This dam pre-exists the TVA period, as well of course as the Army Corps of Engineers period, and the dam remains undercared for, and endangered by

²¹

<https://www.thegleaner.com/story/news/2018/02/25/stinnett-kentucky-river-history-frames-weekend-discovers/364065002/>

²² <http://www.hultgren.org/bridges/>

²³ http://www.coveredbridgesociety.org/downloads/topics_toc.pdf

²⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dix_Dam

²⁵ <https://www.onlyinyourstate.com/kentucky/covered-bridges-ky/>

Dawson Springs, where at least a museum remains to tell the tale. But while Dawson is gone, the Keene Springs Hotel building remains (for now), and one can even go to have brunch in one part, although its days of providing vacancy for the night, appear over.

Left: Keene Hotel; credit: Kaintuckeean²⁶

Many people enjoy stories from the antebellum or pioneer period, and may be keen to visit of the state's famous Halls, such as White Hall, home of Cassius Clay the abolitionist, or Ashland, home of Henry Clay his cousin. Or perhaps one of the many prestigious Louisville homes of the

Clark fame. But what about visiting the strangest and most haunted home in KY, of Confederate Andrew Jackson Caldwell - Octagon Hall (now a museum), in Franklin, KY? The proximity of Franklin to the infamous Jefferson Davis monument (one of the world's tallest obelisks, and completely un-replicable), makes it a great stop on a Civil War/Lincoln tour from Bardstown to Columbus-Belmont SP, which is proximal to the Wickliffe Mounds State Historic Site and museum where you can learn about Mississippian culture, archaeology, and of course architecture (they have example huts in the buildings).

Right: Tower Park credit: author

Heading to the north of the Bluegrass state, of course one should visit the not-so-lost but not-nearly-famous-enough Roebling Bridge²⁷, the predecessor of the world-famous

Brooklyn Bridge.

Enjoy the

Cincinnati area,

and historic Covington cemeteries and the Newport aquarium. But please do not miss a chance to view the magnificent sanctuary of Covington's St. Mary's Cathedral Basilica of the Assumption, which is open to the public (and your cameras!) From there, head

²⁶ <http://www.kaintuckeean.com/2012/07/KeeneSpringsHotel.html>

²⁷ Lower-left: John Roebling Bridge, Covington-Cincinnati; credit:

<https://www.nkytribune.com/2017/01/our-rich-history-150-years-young-the-john-a-roebling-bridge-comes-to-life-on-a-cold-cloudy-day/>

a bit southeast and visit Ft. Thomas to see similar fort monument works as you find in Cincy's Eden Park.

Although you won't find Eden's Park equal at Devou Park, nearby in Ft. Mitchell there is a little known civil war museum, the James A Ramage museum where you can learn about civil war fort types. But, in my opinion, if you want to appreciate unique KY forts of the bygone age, either visit Old Fort Harrod SHS at least to see its record Osage Orange Tree at right²⁸ (and why not Perryville Battlefield while you're there?), Fort Boonesboro SP (and nearby Civil War walking cell-phone tour), Indianfort Mountain in Berea, or go up towards Portsmouth, OH, and see some of the remains of the Portsmouth "Old Fort" earthworks of the Hopewell? There is a unique earthworks Union fort (complete with 10 foot walls and redoubts!) from the civil war near Louisville's Jefferson Memorial Forest and Fort Knox called Fort Duffield (warning: quite a hike, might as well enjoy Tioga Falls National Rec Trail while in the area!)

Last but not least, of course there remain the future enigmatic ruins that will outlast our society well into the hundreds or thousands of years, making for quite the mystery: the iron furnaces. Made of limestone, these relics of the bygone pig iron industry in KY are some of my favorites. The most unique visits are the "lost" ones such as Furnace Mountain²⁹, or Cottage Furnace. But those who prefer to drive will enjoy Clear Creek in Zilpo, Cumberland Gap, and the one you simply have to see in person to appreciate: Fitchburg Furnace. But if you happen to go to Furnace Mountain, there is a real hidden KY Architectural rarity, the Zen Temple with its brilliant blue roof.

Fitchburg Furnace; credit: Estill Co. Dev' Alliance³⁰

²⁸ Credit: author

²⁹ Aka State Rock, a very tall view above the Zen Temple!

³⁰ <http://www.estillcountyky.net/fitchburg-furnace.html>

While I could spend all day mentioning Mill Springs Mill, Yew Dell's tower, the Olde Stone Church, or Olde Talbott Inn, or even the enigmatic Bell Tavern Ruins, the truth is that KY architecture is surprisingly diverse, and spread out. There is no easy way to categorize it all, and this is what makes Kentucky architecture so much fun to study and film. Some of them, even the historic buildings, are endangered, so I also encourage you to support reconstruction efforts such as Georgetown's Ward Hall. But also write to your representatives to complain about the lack of support for deteriorating architecture, such as Falls of Rough mill and dam at Green Farm near the Rough River SRP. You can learn more about these and their locations by visiting hiddendestinationsky.com.

Bell's Tavern Ruins, Park City, KY; credit: author

Hidden Henges in KY

By Sf. Ramon Careaga

Recently I lead a group of people on a small excursion for the Heaven & Earth Society in Lexington to visit Mt. Horeb at Adena Park. I presented about this unique C-henge mound last September, as I believe it is an example of a crater-rim arc discharge. We found some anomalies in the magnetic fields along the crater rim-bridge, which was originally part of a worldwide worship motif. I will return to these motifs in a moment.

Many people are familiar with henge mounds from the British Isles, particularly Wales and Scotland, and near to Stonehenge (which was built by the Welsh-Khumry). However, I just visited a nearly exact copy of the Mt. Horeb mound at Mounds State Park in Anderson, Indiana. Several of the mounds of the Adena exhibit these henge shapes (and were used in addition as worship places, for solstice and equinox markers)

Henge-entrance, the ascent of the cosmic pole towards the center sun³¹ (Indiana); credit: author

This leads the author to consider: how many henge mounds exist which are not yet known? In reviewing the LiDAR from Kentucky From Above while writing the “Great Pyramids of Kentucky” paper, I noticed the following henge located also in Madison County, called Bogie Circle (right).

Just how many of these henges and C-henges exist in the state? This one happens to have a street named for it, but there is zero advertisement of its existence otherwise. Can

³¹ The rim forms the cosmic egg; overall the henge looks a bit like the Cosmic Eye. For more information see the author’s paper “On the Origins of Religions” (Appendix C).

there be more in the state? More like Mt. Horeb or even completely circular henge mounds? This is the object of a future paper I intend to research and write upon this topic. For now let's just simply say that there are likely to be more, perhaps dozens more. And perhaps there were more.

Just what do these henges signify?

Left: Sun glyph symbol³²

The star-god (Kronos) was inside the egg, the cosmic womb, the "aten."

From Budge, "I am the lord of the crown. I am in the Eye, my egg... My seat is on my throne. I sit in the pupil of the Eye."³³

Also, "the sender forth of light into his Circle," and "Lord of the Circles."

Therefore it is my hypothesis that this ancient religion, which has symbols of this exact kind worldwide, including in Kentucky, is ancient and forgotten (for the most part).

The other aspect, the "entrance" into the center (formed, in my opinion during a Birkeland Current discharge of counter rotating cylinders as per Dr. Anthony Peratt and Donald Smith) is used to symbolize the Cosmic Pole, which was also worshiped worldwide (see "The Saturn Myth" by Dave Talbott).

Below: *Cahokia Woodhenge*³⁴

Concentric Circle³⁵ Glyph; credit: Coy et al...³⁶

How can we know that the Adena-Hopewell (Allegewi) peoples were into this religion as well? Perhaps we cannot. But we can look into the Ft. Ancient (Padoucas?³⁷) and the Mississippians /Cahokians and discern from what legends they have left on pottery and in worship. Mainstream archaeology has uncovered

³² Actually, Helios, used to this day for the sun

³³ Papyrus of Ani

³⁴ <https://www.spiritualsun.com/spiritual-sites/cahokia-city-of-the-sun#66>

³⁵ Technically, a hexagon, which is explained thoroughly in author's "Plasma Electromagnetic Sky"

³⁶ "Rock Art of Kentucky" by Coy et al....

³⁷ Lit: White Giants

evidence that, indeed, they also worshipped this cosmic pole and central sun. Thus the archaeologists know Cahokia as the City of the Sun. Of course, they leave out that the Native American Medicine Wheel glyph, used as the Earth symbol, bears no resemblance to the current sun. Also, neither does the sun glyph. Furthermore, how hard would it be to create a miniaturized version of the woodhenge? It would perform the exact same functions. Clearly it meant more than advertised. Compare with a British version (top right: Bryn Celli Ddu³⁸)

Why would mankind go through such efforts to maintain these strike sites by heaping up eroded earth upon them? Or were they making new ones, in order to honor the religions of the ancient ones? This is the mystery left to us, and left worldwide (even, it seems, in the Amazon).

Birkeland Currents, aka magnetic flux ropes, aka galactic jets, transfer considerable amounts of power. Last September I provided some “napkin math” using Maxwell’s classical electromagnetic equations to try and estimate the power.

I am getting closer to find more reasonable models, at least measured *in situ* in our own solar system. Referring to my work in Table 7 of “Magnetic Universe Theory,”³⁹ we find references to electric currents outside of earth at 350 kA. Similarly, the Io-Jupiter current is measured around 600 kA.

Left: *Galactic jet*; credit: *Gabuzda, et al...*⁴⁰

When terrestrial lightning strikes, the stepped leaders start about 100-300 A, and once connection is made, increased to 10-300 kA (avg of 30 kA)⁴¹. When such a strike [allegedly] hit the Earth (according to Delaware Indians, Hindus, and Hebrews), it would surely have been considered the power of God (Wakan-Tanka to native Americans). A better question would be, “Why wouldn’t humans worship at these sites?” They represent the physical imprint of Helios’ power, and this religion was scientific: related to plasma-electromagnetic power. A final question that has been posed, can it really be true that more mounds need to be found, or can be found?

³⁸ <https://medievalheritage.eu/en/main-page/heritage/wales/bryn-celli-ddu-burial-chamber/> 5000-3000 BCE

³⁹ <https://sites.google.com/site/electricuniversegateway/home/research-papers/themagneticuniverseepemcsfrcareaga>

⁴⁰ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>

⁴¹ “The Physics of Lightning,” Dwyer & Uman

Absolutely. On the same trip, I visited Angel Mounds, Indiana, which is another Mississippian culture site. However I learned two things. First across from the visitor center is an Allegewi mound, so the site was clearly important for thousands of years. Second, that in the county next door, at the Mann

Site, a Crab Orchard Hopewell site has been uncovered which is far larger than previously thought, possibly larger overall as a settlement than Chillicothe or even Newark.

Left: Cahokian Cosmogony, Illinois

It's my opinion that these types of sites, despite destruction and despite plowing and "recovery" by state archaeologists will inevitably arise, one by one, to reveal an entire network of

culture, community, and of course travel. A world far more fluid and interesting than the narrative that's been proposed by uniformitarians. A world *covered up* whether by agenda, neglect, or simple mud. Lots, and lots of mud.

I propose, therefore, that we *fan out* and take our work in uncovering a Hidden Kentucky into the level of uncovering all sorts of lost civilizations. It is entirely possible that an entire lost empire or civilization (of a sort) has come and gone, without hardly leaving any imprint. Were they Vikings, or Phoenicians, or someone else? We won't know, until we go. That's why, after finishing "The Great Pyramids of Kentucky,"⁴² I've decided to devote an entire paper to unraveling these pyramid mounds. From Poverty Point to O'Bynam's Fort and Canton, a great number of platforms (step pyramids) have received, in my estimation, a very minimal understanding skipping the Cosmic Mountain motif and failing to connect them with conical mounds. To see a partial list of these pyramids in Kentucky, see my paper's Table 1. It has their designations and dimensions. Further discussions of the motifs mentioned can

also be found in my newest paper, "Ferris Wheels and the Dionysian Irony," located at the Electric Universe Gateway. While we may never know *exactly* what the ancient natives were thinking, or the ancient Brits, could it really be that much different than the Egyptians and Sumerians, who utilized the same motifs and archetypes, glyphs and symbolic languages? Hopefully, through careful analysis and comparative mythology, we shall find out. See you on the road.

Platform Pyramid, Angel Mounds SHS, Indiana;

credit: author

⁴² https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final

Transported Through Time

By Sf. Ramon Careaga

This project consumes a lot of time. Think about time for a moment: the measurement of the passage of events. When time began for man, it was a completely new concept⁴³ (demarcation of discrete values for time). Now it is one of our most precious resources.

When I drive through Kentucky in search of rare and unique destinations, my mind tends to ‘jump’ timelines.

Sometimes it jumps into alternate timelines, but most of the time my mind is on rewind. I try to viscerally insert my mind into the backwards flow and pick up sensations from those remote places. But I must admit, I’m not always successful. This is due to our natural *nowness* filter which causes us to project our current culture, thoughts, feelings, memories, and experiences *onto* the past, rather than feeling them as they were. So, for example when I visited the Rathskeller Museum⁴⁴ in the basement of the Historic Seebach in Louisville (upper right), I was not able to truly “ghost in.” I could sense the past of Al Capone’s alleged secret bar. I could imagine the *nowness* of it, the revelry and the entertainment, despair and business. But I couldn’t physically feel it for myself. I felt like I only witnessed the spectres but was not among them. It was an *alien* feeling for me.

Contrast this with my trip that day to Mundy’s Landing at the Kentucky River. I was barely there but for a few brief moments, but instantly I could sense the very air of pioneering. Imagine it: a land of endless trees and game, basically untamed. Easily exotic to the ear (just imagine for the Spanish and French, and Chinese!) and intense. Those KY River Palisades cliffs might seem tame, but they are plenty foreboding. The river would have been wild, and sometimes quiet as a tomb. One might even feel as

though eyes were above you, waiting for a chance to make it your tomb.

⁴³ https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_is_the_oldest_historical_record_of_human_existence_historical_artifact

⁴⁴ Upper right: Rathskeller; Bottom-left: Mundy’s Landing. Those are 200’ cliffs in the background

But the pioneers overcame this primal place, and put to work in turning it to business and

livelihood. They erased all but the hint traces of the former aeons, and in turn we have erased their era with modernity and industry. Although the KY River no longer has any commercial traffic, it retains the ghosts of it. An uneasy quiet of progress disturbed. Industry that stretched down these various Kentucky rivers into the Great River, which went on to the ocean, and provided transport of lumber, livestock, shells, minerals, copper, tobacco, pig iron, and everything else. Suddenly: halted. Replaced yes by the highway

and railway systems, but also by a people of generally isolationist mentality (so not too different than pioneers?) What would it be like to encounter this exotic land? Much of what pioneer frenzy has survived to this day came from later travels, such as those of Lewis & Clark, or of the Alaska-Yukon gold rush, or of Montanans or Californians trying to make their gold. But the actual start of the movement west here in Kentucky is generally left to the teachings at old forts and museums to convey. Some have excellent video or historical renditions (as they have at Fort Boonesboro for sale on DVD). But even then, one can feel the presence of the camera crew, and the relatively shallow penetration to the *real sense* of the past. For the most part, filmmaking pioneer video in Kentucky on location is limited by the extremely young forests, and lack of mountain lions, bison, etc... and addition of modern features. Another thing is that Kentucky had a *lot* of wetland in those days, which was drained off or filled in. Lexington and Louisville both were wetlands.

Now, the issue of time traveling on locations is also hampered by a disconnect in public education. Most locations have nearby historic signs, but many do not. And their inner reality may not be for public consumption. You can go visit the Filson, or the Jefferson Community College⁴⁵, but some places simply require permission to enter.

⁴⁵ Upper left: Filson Historical Society; Bottom: Jefferson Community College (Louisville both)

It may take more than a passing photo or drive. In which case, one will need to separately arrange a visit and this is problematic. Most of the time you will be engaging the scholarly or intellectual by acting as a tourist or even researcher (amateur or otherwise). This will put up a real barrier within you, and then you have to somehow penetrate this shell to then pierce the shell of the location. It's far better if you find a location where you can be left alone for a time to gaze into a house object, photo, or painting. A very few historic buildings even allow you to sit on the furniture. If you can be left alone for a few minutes, you just *might* soak in the environment and come away wholly different. Whenever someone is talking at or to you, they are guiding your mind into a narrative, and that is antithetical to what I call "world popping."

As a rule I only take a few tours yearly because of this. I prefer if anything, to be left to reading and studying the environment, and trying to sniff out latent energy. Of course almost everything has a restored or altered sense to it. Some, like the Mary Todd Lincoln home had to be restored completely. Others, one can simply tell much has been altered. Few locations are like White Hall or Ashland or William Whitley SHS where you can genuinely feel the pioneer and antebellum and postbellum life pumping through the grounds. Many places try to keep it alive, such as Shaker Village at Pleasant Hill (which has a lovely preserve attached). But it simply has scant traces of that old energy left. This is probably why I love to visit mid-central Kentucky where far fewer visitors have been (like Octagon Hall).

So: give it a try. Go travelling throughout Kentucky, Ohio, and Indiana and try out these latent senses. Shut off the intellect and take in the world through the lens alone. Feel out the past, and imagine the very air. It may be advisable, if you struggle, to make your way to the Daniel Boone National Forest (or on my parkway layout on hiddendestinationsky.com) to first feel the wild air. Alternates of course would be some of the old growth forests throughout the Caintuck. But whatever you do, let the modernity drop away as much as possible, and *insert* your psyche into the very place and, yes, time. It may provide, if nothing else, a helpful diversion. It may even be therapeutic!

Bogie Circle (subject of last newsletter), Madison County; What were they doing here?

Dogfoot Hollow or Bust

by Sf. Ramon Careaga

On November 10th, 2018, members Bruce Grimes, Chris Dunlap, Andy Careaga and myself set out to explore the upper reaches of Dogfoot Hollow, a site that was informed to Ramon by a Berea/Red Lick Valley local. Exciting ceramic finds had been made in the creek below, previously (see right). In a 2017 hike, I had explored the site, not knowing what to expect. I discovered it was a) incredibly steep, b) strategically viable, and c) tiered with titillating and unusual rock formations at the third tier. However, I was unable to explore further then due to safety concerns.

This year, we returned **in force**, and brought our ragtag group up *to* the height of the site, using ropes and a grappling hook, helping each other to remain safe. What we found was not definitive proof of a stone fort, perse, but a geological wonderland that also possibly could belie a strategic technological place. But this cannot be proven without some samples taken. Unfortunately our geologist friend Kim Blackburn could not make it this time, so

we have no professional report of the materials. However, here's what we found:

Left: from 2017 hike to Tier 2⁴⁶

The Tiered layers do provide an excellent defensible position, over a commanding view. The proximity of historic taverns and civil war action opens up the possibility to the site being used in a historical context.

But there were no signs of modern use or visitation above Tier 1. Below tier 1, there is a logging road, pollution/dumping, and signs of hunting. Tier 2 is extremely dangerous and only the use of the "Artificial stairs", which

still remain to my eye, too convenient, enables further ascent. It may be possible to descend to Tier 3 from the ridge far above, and Chris did explore this possibility. However, from Tier 2 up to 3, there is a convenient switchback feature of the cliff.

⁴⁶ The "adobe" layer is actually soft limestone, and the "doorway" as seen from tier 1 was actually not full height. The point may be manmade, and is at the height of a head. But the window starts at waist high.

Tier 3 (left) and Tier 2 (right), overlooking Tier 1 to valley; Soft Limestone with overhang

Top: acid etching below “Doorway”; fault? Breccias in horizontal 1 foot layer

Bottom-left: Tier 3 ... wide enough for cannon

Bottom-right: natural column in soft limestone layer. Bed area to right and left of column would hold perhaps a half dozen men.

Massive acid etched column; looks to be natural, but it is highly unusual, and different along cliff

Left: “Stone bed”⁴⁷

Right: Narrow passage from Upper Ridge

The “adobe” like layer which from Tier 2 appears artificial and added, is actually a natural, but restricted limestone formation that is different than the other limestone. The gap above it is owing to the differential erosion rate of the sandstone/mudstone layer (ancient beach) above that, which erodes fast. However the limestone was also inset, and this created three unique features:

- 1) the “Doorway” - not a doorway but a “window” which led to a 20-30’ narrow passageway, probably occupied by animals. It does appear to have vitrification of the sides, and possible carbon scoring. Acid marks below also have a minor possibility of being artificial, giving this triangular window the appearance of a furnace.
- 2) The acid erosion: dripping concentrated water with carbonic acid is much more potent below this window feature. It really isn’t happening elsewhere on Tier 3’s level. Between Tier 3 and 2 is a hard limestone layer of 12’ or so, and it has numerous vertical hollowed columns. But at this time I think they are the result of repetitious dripping, and as Bruce pointed out, may be owing to higher concentrations or acids that are stronger due to organic materials or other layers unseen. The window is **not** a waterfall, but fracturing may lead more water to this feature. Andy also pointed out the breccias or concretions which were forming in the layer.
- 3) Rock shelters: several person would have been capable of sleeping in the multicolored gaps formed between the soft limestone (the limited layer) and the sandstone overhang. Some signs of burning appeared there, but certainly nothing recent.

The view was absolutely spectacular, and with trees cleared would have been commanding. Easy coordination with Indianfort, Pilot Knob, and Big Hill gap would be possible. Furthermore, as the members can attest, approach to the upper Tiers is prohibitive and easily defendable. If the site was not used strategically, as a place to produce something in a furnace, it would be surprising or disappointing. Tier 1 is eroded but the soil is loamy. Pawpaw groves cover the area and grow well, but agriculture would be less likely than subsistence.

⁴⁷ One of the “pseudo glyphs” we found on this, but appears to be naturally etched.

In the distance a small highway was just visible (left of center)

Left: apparent vitrification or rounding (by fire?) Right: carbon/soot? or black lichen?

Left: Bruce in window (furnace? kiln?)

Right: limestone below, fallen mudstone above

Left: Andy finds edible (but overripe) mushrooms

Right: upper pass to Ridge?

No glyphs were found but strange formations abound, some of them open to interpretation⁴⁸. There were no signs of modernity up in the upper tiers. Multiple rock shelters made the final leg of the journey up quite comfortable and we were easily able to spend hours at the top. From Tier 3 to Tier 1 was a more than 3 second fall (as the stone falls), so about 140'. From Tier 1 to the roadway was not an easy hike by any means (due to mud and ascent), perhaps another 100'. So defensible advantages would be had,

⁴⁸ Bottom-right: Naturally etched Awen? Taken as presented (facing entrance)

and the creek originating in the hollow would provide a constant water source.

Left: remarkable but limited calcite formations

At the end of the trek downwards attempts were made to scavenge in the creekbed, but a future trip to sift the soil will be conducted. Nothing was found, but there were signs of other human use, and perhaps the area is fished out for native artifacts by locals. Fruit and stone markers were found which suggest other visitors near the roadway. A visit in May is tentatively scheduled,

although the Sand Island trip and Bruce's trips may cause a jostling of planned outings.

Safety being paramount, I am happy to report the only casualty was Chris' water bottle. Several killer stones were removed which made for an exciting adventure. The find of the day belonged to Andy, who found a naturally made "Eternal Terrarium" that had become sporadically planted inside an old water bottle. The fern had a uniquely warm and moist existence, albeit limited and lonely!

Though we found less than I hoped for, we discovered more than we had a right to expect! The site remains intriguing and the possibility of artifact recovery remains potent enough to justify further work.

Andy's New Eternal Terrarium

All of the photos and video can be found at: <http://bit.ly/2z5Gjz9>

Hidden Springs' History

By Sf. Ramon Careaga

It is a continual source of amazement for me that on each trip I go out something new arises. On December 30th, 2018 I took a trip out towards the Broke Leg Falls area to catalog Knocking Cave Creek Falls, which isn't an easy hike and cannot be done in overgrown summer. I also desired to stop at the Swamp Valley Museum in Denniston, KY. All of this went without a hitch. However during the drive

back from Frenchburg, heading west on KY 36 through one of my favorite localities, Olympia (so named for the knob, Mt. Olympus). . . .It was there, right next to the junction for the road that used to lead to the now defunct (and sold into private hands) lands of the Olympic State Forest, was a hidden marker.

Technically it wasn't hidden on purpose. It was located behind a cedar on one side, and a row of trees and hedges otherwise covered in leaves. What made this marker special was that it was located next to a historic cemetery (left).

What this inspired me about was the hidden,

unspoken/untaught history in Kentucky of the springs' resorts boom and bust. Back in the early to mid 1800's, when Kentucky was still the West - when Lexington was known as "The Athens of the West" - there was a rush and tourism explosion of herbal/health tonic spas. In the 1800's there was a general desire on both sides of the ocean to achieve spiritual cleanliness and (of course) physical well being. It was generally believed that mineral springs and hot springs could provide such things. I believe this as well, and in my personal experience with springs, there are extremely beneficial effects for bathing in mineral springs.⁴⁹

Despite the fact that Kentucky's springs are not hot, there are several places where the limestone and sulphur well springs not only attracted tourists, even throngs of people, but entire resorts sprung up and thrived for decades. A few even bottled (in

Kentucky had at least 50 spas located on or near mineral springs. Resort owners would build large hotels, private cabins, bathhouses, steam rooms, and pools. These resorts offered the wealthy an important social environment for those seeking refuge from intense summer heat or the pollution of the cities. Resorts had riding stables, ballrooms, saloons for the men, music and dancing (including fancy dress and costume balls), gambling, billiards, fishing, and hunting. The most fashionable spa in Kentucky was built in 1828 by Dr. Christopher Columbus Graham, owner of Harrodsburg and Greenville Springs, but sold the property in 1853 for the Western Military Asylum (a home for retired soldiers). The most popular and long-lived spas in Kentucky were Olympian Springs (Bath Co.), Crab Orchard Springs (Lincoln Co.), and Blue Lick Springs (Nicholas Co.). For more information see J. Winston Coleman, Springs of Kentucky (Lexington, Ky., 1955).

⁴⁹ <http://www.uky.edu/~dolph/sites/springs.html>

glass) the water and sold it, both for medicinal value and taste. It was the economy for many of the towns that came into existence. Unfortunately, all of it came to a crashing end with a series of cholera epidemics which caused rashes of deaths and a dwindling in interest (obviously) because of the incredible fear engendered by the deadly disease.

Big Bone Lick Springs (Boone County) - birthplace of American vertebrate archaeology. Known for the mineral sulphur springs which are still active at the state park. It is known as the famous Boone Salt Springs as it was a place where salt was rapidly acquired through a boiling method. At that time, salt was not as easily acquired as it is now, and it was an incredibly important preservative commodity. The salt springs were the primary reason so many megafauna and natives visited the site yearly, for millions of years. Now it is a tourist destination with a visitor center, but the springs remain quite full.

Blue Lick Springs (Nicholas County)- *“Thousands of invalids visited the Springs, seeking and obtaining health; and, as a consequence, the fashionable world made them a noted pleasure resort. Thomas and Louis Hollady, having leased the property from Major Bedinger about the year 1842, erected a hotel on a vast scale, and under their courtly and liberal management the place rose to a renown second to none in the United State even the celebrated Saratoga Springs, of New York, being the only rival. The BLUE LICKS was the favorite summer resort of the wealthy and refined southern planters and merchants, with their families.”*^{50 51} (sic)

Crab Orchard Springs (Lincoln County) - *“Historical Marker #152 in Crab Orchard notes the popular mineral springs resort that operated there for almost one hundred years. Eight natural mineral springs were located at Crab Orchard. Three of the springs contained iron-heavy water, two produced salt water, and three others provided different types of sulfur water. In 1827, entrepreneur Jack Davis established the first resort, and, by the 1860s, Crab Orchard Springs had developed into one of the most sought after hydrotherapy resorts in Kentucky. Advertisements ran in Kentucky newspapers touting the curative powers of the waters and offering information on stagecoach lines to the springs. In 1871, a fire destroyed the main hotel building at Crab Orchard Springs, but, under the supervision of the site’s owner, Isaac Shelby III, a new hotel was constructed that featured more than 250 rooms.”*⁵² (sic)

Dawson Springs - Dawson Springs, KY is known as the home of Governor Steve Beshear, but long before he was born, there was a massive resort and bottling operation that employed hundreds of people. Though it fell from favor, the aquifer remains very strong, and at one time nearly became the home of a modern bottling plant. At this time, a modest museum remains across the street from the location of the original hotel. The site even has a connection to Professor Rafinesque himself.⁵³

Drennon Springs (Henry County) - Like many of the springs on this list, the flourishing of Drennon Springs, which is located near to the unique Drennon Falls, was the cholera epidemic. The hotel also burned down in 1909.⁵⁴ A fascinating amount of history is associated with this spring, located in northern KY, and going all the way back to 1773; including the interest of General George Rogers Clark. Again it was at first the salt and game which was of interest, but health benefits became one of the prime focuses in the early 1800s.

“In 1780 an Archibald Dickerson thought he discovered a silver vein in the vicinity of two of the springs. It was

⁵⁰ “The Arlington, the Genuine Blue Lick Water”

https://archive.org/stream/TheArlington/TheArlington_djvu.txt

⁵¹ <https://www.kyatlas.com/ky-blue-licks.html>

⁵² <https://explorekyhistory.ky.gov/items/show/567>

⁵³ <http://dawsonspringsky.com/trails/history.htm>

⁵⁴ https://www.newspapers.com/clip/22794209/drennon_springs_hotel_goes_up_in/

really sulfide of lead. The mining of lead ore for its silver content began on the Drennon Springs vein in 1783. Willard Jillson, a former state geologist, identifies this as the "first lead mine 'in Kentucky." Desired results were not achieved so work stopped until around 1815.

The pioneers learned from friendly Indians the use that they had made of the sulphur water from one of the springs. The medicinal use of the waters soon spread beyond the neighborhood. In 1833 Asiatic Cholera spread throughout Kentucky. The proprietor advertised that Drennon Springs was the "safest retreat from cholera in Kentucky." By 1840 the Springs were known not only as refuge for the sick but a site of entertainment for those who were desiring a better social life after putting their economic affairs in order. Large numbers of Kentuckians were joined by wealthy cotton and sugar cane planters who came to avoid the hot weather and yellow fever prevalent in the southern summers. Trade between the regions was facilitated and the Springs and the marriage market became synonymous terms.

A. O. Smith purchased the property, spent about \$100,000 on improvements including several multi-level structures for housing and planted trees on newly terraced land. In 1848 the owner announced in the Louisville Daily Courier that they could accommodate 800 persons. Innumerable governors, social headliners of the day, and the grandchildren of Henry Clay came to visit. At the height of the resort's popularity in 1849 cholera broke out. The hotel complex was abandoned within 24 hours. Faith was lost in the miraculous waters. For two years the hotel lay idle."⁵⁵ (sic)

After this the springs hotel was used as a military school, barracks, and refuge for invalids. It was eventually lost to history, perhaps because of a chickenpox epidemic, perhaps for insurance money. At this time ruins are all that remains, and a historical marker.

Grayson Springs (Grayson, KY) - "Established by M.P. Clarkson, this colonial style Inn flourished from 1825 to the 1920s as a health spa. Springs containing salt, alum, copper, and white, black, or red sulfur were supposed to cure a vast number of illnesses, including cholera. Kentuckians were besieged with cholera epidemics in 1833 and 1849. The Grayson Springs spa reached its height in 1900 under the ownership of the Mercke brothers. As advertised in the Leitchfield Gazette in 1903, guests at Grayson Springs enjoyed "the most noted waters in America," from more than twenty springs. However, scientific innovations in medicine were providing more effective means of curative powers, and improved transportation was making other vacation spots (like Niagara Falls) more luring for the pleasure-hunters. The few remaining health spas situated around mineral springs were in rapid decline.

A series of fires destroyed the original four hotels in 1909, and a rebuilt hotel burned down in 1930. The sole remaining structure was purchased in 1947. In 1955, it reopened and for several years was a gathering place for special occasions. Today, this privately-owned building is all that remains of that era."^{56 57 58} (sic)

Keene Springs (Keene, KY) - The Keene Springs Inn shares a similar story to others on this list except that the Hotel remains. It is, of course not in use as a hotel or inn, although there is one brunch related event which takes place there. Keene is a small town on KY 33, and this hotel really is worth passing through to see. It is one of the last remaining hidden gems of the Bluegrass which is in almost the same shape now as it was during the post-bellum period.

McConnell Springs (Lexington) - This is the springs that started Lexington. It is a blue hole spring, one of only a few remaining in the entire state. A Blue Hole is a vertical spring. Today McConnell Springs is a state preserve with a visitor/education center, and a wildlife pond as well as easy to walk trails. It is open

⁵⁵ <https://www.history.henrycountky.com/drennon/drenhist.htm>

⁵⁶ Ibid., Jody Henderson, May 9, 1997

⁵⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Grayson_Springs,_Kentucky

⁵⁸ <https://explorekyhistory.ky.gov/items/show/644>

to the public daily for free. It is always under threat by industry which surrounds the springs, including quarries. Displays along the trail demonstrate the fascinating geology of this year-round spring.

Mill Springs (Wayne County) - Mill Springs is located on KY 90, and is home to historical ruins of the medicinal springs but remaining museums associated with the water mill there. They still hold daily water mill demonstrations on site, and visitors can also enjoy the gift shop, overlook, historic homes, and the magnificent travertine waterfalls which dump into Lake Cumberland. The energy is very charged with negative ions, and gives an extremely healthy aura. Just sitting at the bench is good enough for a nice recharge.

Old Graham Springs (Harrodsburg) - This spring is the reason why Old Fort Harrod was built, becoming Kentucky's first permanent city. Unfortunately the fort's has been destroyed and the current fort is relocated nearby as the original was removed due to age and rotting timbers. There is a recreation of the spring at the new site, which is fed via tap. Like so many of these year long springs, they were controlled by the officers in order to protect the water source.

Nearby is the still extant Graham-Sutton Springs, which has a long and rich history as well⁵⁹, and the

Greenville Springs, "*Greenville Springs opened in the first decade of the 19th century (owner Tobias Eastland), with nearly 1500 guests (including physicians) registered over the course of the 1808 season. The following year, new buildings were added to the grounds, including a hotel with a 112-foot long porch and a ballroom, as well as stables. The resort was purchased in 1812 by Henry Palmer; who further improved the grounds over the next seven year, adding bathhouses, a bar of "extensive proportions," cottages (extending the capacity to 300 guests at a time), a large dining room, a theatre (advertisements claimed a "regular theatrical company of respectable performers"), and a pleasure garden [3, 6]. The property was purchased by Dr. Christopher Graham in the summer of 1827. Captain David Sutton opened Harrodsburg Springs as a spa in 1807, managed by John G. Chiles until Dr. Christopher Graham purchased the property (60-70 acres) for \$10,000 in November of 1828. Under Graham's management, the two resorts were renamed Graham Springs (though sometimes were still referred to as Harrodsburg Springs), and improvements and expansion began [3]. In 1829, the grounds included a bandstand, a ballroom (50 by 100 feet), bathhouses, two rows of cabins, a battledore [badminton] court, and a bowling alley. The new brick hotel (1842-1843) was four stories high and capable of accommodating 1,000 guests, featuring a long colonnaded promenade, a second ballroom (50 by 100 feet), a 150-person dining room, an "elegant saloon," and a gaming room for chess and backgammon.*

The grounds had been expanded to 280 acres by 1850, with an artificial lake, a grotto, an ice-house, an aqueduct and reservoir, walking and riding paths, three additional bowling alleys, bathhouses, warm showers and steam rooms, whole avenues of private cottages for wealthy guests, and a boardwalk through a grove of locust trees led from the hotel to the springs [3, 10]. Octagonal gazebos stood atop the springhouses at the Saloon Spring and Graham's Spring; water was carried by employees from the springs to "treatment rooms" at the hotel, equipped with showers and tub baths [1]. A "professor of dancing" was hired to conduct cotillion parties, fancy dress and masquerade balls were held in the two ballrooms, and Graham owned a band of slave musicians who provided entertainment at the springs during the summer months and were hired out to perform in Louisville during the winter months (three of the musicians escaped to Canada in 1841) [1, 3, 6].

Why Graham sold the property to the United States Government in 1853 is not clear in the historic literature; it was purchased for \$100,000 for use as a military asylum for disabled veterans, but fire destroyed the main buildings in 1859 and the patients were moved to a Washington, D.C. asylum." ⁶⁰ (sic)

⁵⁹ <https://kentuckykindredgenealogy.com/2018/03/09/graham-springs-famous-waters-bring-many-to-mercier-county/>

⁶⁰ <https://www.theclio.com/web/entry?id=21629>

*"Graham Springs Hotel. "The Saratoga Of The South". (Printed verso reads: "No vacation is complete in the Blue-Grass without a visit to Graham Springs Hotel, Old Fort Harrod, and the historic and pioneer town of Harrodsburg, Ky. 100 miles from Cincinnati, 75 miles from Louisville, 30 miles from Lexington, 7 miles from Shakertown, Dix Dam and Herrington Lake. Good roads in every direction. Sole owners of Greenville and Graham Springs Mineral Water declared by analysis to be the only saline waters of worth found in the United States (see U.S. Dispensatory, page 106)."*⁶¹

Olympic Springs (Bath County) - *"With over ten springs of saline-sulfur, chalybeate (water containing iron compounds), and white sulfur waters, a boarding house and cabins were built on the site (known as Mud Lick or Mud Lick Springs) as early as 1791 [4, 5, 7, 8, 1]. As of the early 1870s, the grounds included a black sulfur spring, a saline-sulfur well (diuretic but not laxative), a white sulfur spring about half a mile from the well (which began flowing after the 1811 New Madrid Earthquake), and from a pair of chalybeate springs (about 40 yards apart, half a mile from the well) [2, 4].*

The springs were accessible by the Lexington and Big Sandy Railroad, which stopped at Mount Sterling; from there, a stagecoach brought guests to the springs, 35 miles from the station.

Colonel Thomas Hart changed the name to Olympian Springs (sometimes referred to as Olympia Springs) when he purchased the property in 1800 and established the first hotel (with a dining room large enough for 100 guests). Three years later, Kentucky's first stage route was established between Lexington and Olympian Springs; by 1804, according to a letter from Henry Clay to Colonel Hart, "The Olympian Springs are the constant topic of conversation. 'Do you not intend to go there this season?' is a question put to everyone, and nobody answers it in the negative,"

On October 19, 1864, during a Civil War battle at Olympia Springs, many of the cabins were burned, but the resort recovered [7]. After the Civil War, the lost cabins were replaced and the bathing rooms renovated; the resort's amenities and activities included cards, billiards, horse racing, music, dancing, bathing, swings, riding, and hunting (a hunting dog pack was kept on site for guests). The Chesapeake and Ohio Railroad stopped near Olympia, and the resort kept hacks and omnibuses waiting at the station to transport guests [6, 7]. The resort continued operation into

⁶¹ https://exploreuk.uky.edu/catalog/xt7x696zwx82_1_4858

the 1940s, but according to the literature as of 1984, "nothing remains of this 19th century vacation and health resort,"⁶² (sic)

Paroquet Springs (Bullitt County) - *"One of the largest and most popular watering places of its day was located only a few miles from Louisville, Kentucky. Its name is known chiefly to the descendants of long-established families in the area where it once flourished, but even they know it only as a tradition, and details of its history have grown dim and difficult to discover. The spa was Paroquet Springs, and it was situated near Shepherdsville in Bullitt County, just nineteen miles southeast of Louisville. This is the story as it has unfolded from information long buried in old court records and in family letters, many of which are housed in manuscript collections in The Filson Club Historical Society. It answers many questions about the origin, operation, and demise of the famous spa but leaves others unanswered. Perhaps with this beginning, more information will come to light so that a complete history of Paroquet Springs can someday be written."*⁶³

The Public Spring (Scottville) - Not a bathing spring, but a historically significant source of water that was both reliable and long-lived.⁶⁴

Royal Springs (Georgetown) - Another historically significant drinking spring that is still under operation. *"Royal Spring Park is the site of a large spring in Georgetown, Kentucky that since the earliest settlements in the area has provided water for the area. In addition to the spring, the park has a log cabin built by a former slave, Milton Leach."*⁶⁵ (sic)

Sulphur Well (Metcalf County) - Historic Sulphur Well Park has been covered in a previous article. It still runs, although the heyday of the resort is over. You can, however visit the wonderful Lighthouse restaurant and then get some of the magical water in the park across the street. It smells of eggs but the old timers still swear by it.

*"Ezekiel Neal began acquiring land along the South Fork in Metcalfe County in 1832. In 1845 he began digging a well. With a hand and horse powered drill he hit water at a depth of 180 feet. The stream of water has flowed continually since then. Mr. Neal was attempting to hit a salt well, as one had been dug on the East Fork of the Little Barren River and was making money for the owner. Disappointingly, this well was not a salt well. The water was analyzed and found to contain Sulphur, Magnesia, Salt and Iron. This combination of chemicals was believed to cure stomach problems and nervous disorders."*⁶⁶ (sic)

Above: Remains of Buena Villa Hotel at Sulphur Well⁶⁷

⁶² <https://www.theclio.com/web/entry?id=21627>

⁶³ "THE PURSUIT OF HEALTH AND HAPPINESS AT THE PAROQUET SPRINGS IN KENTUCKY. 1838 TO 1888," Audrea McDowell,

"This was originally published in the Filson Club History Quarterly, Vol. 69, No. 4, October 1995, pages 390-420. Audrea McDowell was at that time the manuscript cataloger at The Filson Club Historical Society, and the author of a number of articles on state and local history."

<https://bullittcountyhistory.org/bchistory/ps.html> Long but a very good read. Lots of Presidential history in this one.

⁶⁴ <http://www.allencountyky.com/database/misc/spring.html>

⁶⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Royal_Spring_Park

⁶⁶ <https://www.kentuckytourism.com/historic-sulphur-well-park/>

⁶⁷ <https://sites.google.com/site/historyofsulphurwellkentucky/assignments>

The Riddle of the Spratt Stone City

By Sf. Ramon Careaga

In January there was a short snap of warm weather with good energy and lighting, and I was able to go out to Frenchburg on a mission. It was the fourth time stopping by in the area. I had my brother with me for some good family time. What was the mission? To finally locate the Spratt stone “serpent” and Running Man shape, and see for myself this infamous lost city. You can hear tale of it on the internet, or even better, by buying Lee Pennington’s DVD biopic on old man Spratt himself⁶⁸. But none of these will be enough. The entire area reeks of mystery.

Take for example the nearby (up on the ridge) “Devil’s Markethouse Arch,”⁶⁹ where I had quite the adventure and the energy was definitely odd. The arch gives one the feeling of a carved temple and/or altar, the way it sits out on its lonesome away from all other ridges (unlike any other arch except Zilpo Arch, which is a limestone formation to the north of Frenchburg). Take also the crossing of the Sheltoewe trail, which is undoubtedly based upon previous footpaths through some of the densest jungle of Kentucky.

It’s across from the old Spratt/Layne farm⁷⁰ that the mystery deepens, and what I discovered truly astounded me. It is, I believe, clear evidence of sophisticated fortification techniques and deliberate strategic choices. I do not have what is called definitive

⁶⁸ “Good Water Good Roads: The Life Of Verne Spratt”

http://www.joleproductions.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=6&Itemid=3

⁶⁹ Right: arch, credit: author

⁷⁰ Top: image source, Kentucky From Above; prominence is in center-right of photo

proof. But the summation of the unique facts, along with my suspicions means that I have a strong desire to continue my research in the area.

SPRATT SITE, CLIFTON CREEK, MENIFEE COUNTY, KENTUCKY

(C) 1994 Lee Pennington

CODE FOR FINDS AT SPRATT PLACE

1. Verne & Ida Mae Spratt House
2. Original Archaeology site with snake wall, snake head in rockhouse, 23 plus stone mounds.
3. Snake wall, stone mounds, snake effigy in rockhouse, trident-awenturkey track on small rock down from rockhouse, dirt mound.
4. Indian Smoke Chimney, caves in cliff, some petroglyphs on rocks down from cliff, old claymine.
5. 2500' to 3000' long Archaeology site with snake wall broken in places perhaps from past timbering roads, 73 plus mounds (located at either end of wall) with largest number at west end.
6. Rockhouse with strange fill dirt (several tons brought in apparently).
7. The Sinks (40 plus acres), old coalmine at upper end.
8. Rockhouse with initials (reportedly Swift), date 1767 on wall .
9. Rockhouse with running man petroglyphs, (left-hand petroglyph and arrow destroyed), nutting holes in form of snake.
10. Large rockhouse, several nutting holes, place reported that box with golden calf retrieved, Buffalo Rock is nearby.
11. Large rockhouse with initials, the word MIKE or MINE, circles on wall, nutting holes; site has been worked with backhoe.
12. Direction of Wynn Hollow where large stone has several circle crosses and other symbols, turkey track; stone beside larger one apparently covered with tiny writing on one face; odd looking stone (Earth Mother?). Hollow below this area (before Dock Hollow) reportedly had vault opened that contained English crowns.
13. Direction of Devil's Marketplace; on ridge is Spratt's Turtle Back Rock, nearby stone with circle cross. Out ridge is hole in rocks where one can see the sky; smelting furnace reportedly found in first hollow east from Marketplace, waterfalls at head of Long Branch.

Figure supplied by Lee Pennington, from previous survey.

Consider the following topographical advantages:

- A sharp ridgeline above with no easy descent
- One entrance in: the holler mouth, except the creek from the south.
- Fresh and continuous water supply
- A large rockshelter hollow that leads to known glyph markings, and some type of mineral working
- A large 2 tier semicircular fortifiable hill, with a large top stop ridge that could easily be defended or hidden.
- Known population of hundreds, if not thousands of people (dozens of remaining mounds *after* logging can be found, and many more are probably somewhat obscured by brush and erosion. More also sit across the road behind the Spratt house, and perhaps more in hidden locations.
- A serpentine wall-like structure atop a flattened road-like position. This road might have been totally modern and related to logging, but the mounds rested upon it rather comfortably.
- Multiple prominences for creating ambushades, which would be excellent lookouts and difficult to attack directly. Definitely majestic, and if they are natural, certainly odd.
- One example of a potential redoubt - or a missing toppled tree that created a perfect hollow in the soil so long ago no traces of the tree can be found.

Left: Mound in remarkably good shape

Right: Remains of wall formation, or mill?

- TL: interlocking stones on mound
- TR: mounds being swallowed by erosion
- ML: headstone with glyphs pointed out
- MR: more of wall feature around fort
- BL: ambuscades (3 of 4) with good spacing and height
- BR: side view, a good 16-20' height advantage for archers

Left: Mystery ridge/home hidden behind Rhododendron jungle? Conveniently blocked!?
Right: Perfect slope for slowing advance but not impossible to build upon. This is the 2nd tier

Now, although I did not see any glyphic evidence myself, as the road to the rockshelter was now closed on account of Mr. Layne moving on (or passing on), and the land being controlled by neighbors, I did manage to find a similar headstone feature that was exactly reminiscent of that which I found at the stone fortification that I found proximal to the Russellville “Lost City”. Upright perpendicularly, for no apparent reason, and a generally triangular point. I noted what appeared to me to be two very faded, almost impossible to get detail of glyphs on that headstone, but they could just have as easily been natural features.

All in all the site impressed upon me the same military air that I felt at Alabama’s Moundville, and Arkansas’ Toltec Mounds SP. A power resided there at Spratt, and not for a temporary time but as a place of permanence, just like the “Lost City”. It seemed to me to probably be of the same culture. Given the infamous nature of the Russellville site, and its stone coffins, I cannot help but expect that beneath these mostly pristine mounds, more stone coffins will be found. I was also impressed with the interlocking nature of the stones, now covered in healthy moss, which indicated more care than a mere cairn would be granted. It wasn’t like other stone and dirt piles, it was ever so slightly more sophisticated. It was not hard for me to imagine the remains of either an advanced race of native warriors, or travellers from a distant land. Perhaps the Welsh were really here, in Frenchburg, up in a holler, living their lives free of the worries of the Old World. Or maybe they were holed up there, escaping a very hostile New World, and separated by miles from other settlements that had been made in Kathiki.

Many years ago at Natural Bridge I was struck by the Avalonesque feeling the view gave me as I looked upon our comely knobs. Not quite as tame as the Shire, but not quite as vertically remote as the Alps. A far more distant feeling of fantasy: a nostalgia for a place I’d never been, and a time I did not personally know came over me. And writing this I am reminded of that far off ‘isle’ of promise, that has ever eluded western culture. Where is a place in the world where Justice and freedom can be had, without the oppression of enemies, and the bothersome meddling of political turmoil? Perhaps the Spratt city was as real to Avalon as can ever be found, because after all, it is so remote and removed from notice, that even despite the AKHA **giving** a site survey to the University of Kentucky Office of State Archaeology... no one has bothered to protect or enter the site, and delve into it from a mainstream perspective. With

NAGPRA it is unlikely to happen in this century. So for many years still, the secret of the potential fort, and its long dead secrets may remain - hopefully - secure and preserved, along a jungle covered hillside, deep in the heart of the Daniel Boone National Forest.

The Pyramid Ages in Kentucky

by Sf. Ramon Careaga

We've already seen a factual description of the amazing engineering at Giza, from learned engineers like Chris Dunn⁷¹. We have found the electrical behaviors in the pyramids⁷². We have seen that the Mayans also had constellation aligned pyramids, and they, too, had piezoelectric mica⁷³ installed on their own construction efforts (probably less for making a power plant than attracting plasma to commune with the spirit world). Now your truly has found that here in Kentucky, as recent as 1100 AD there were Cygnus aligned pyramid mounds⁷⁴ (in Madison County), and that they may have been the work of pre-Columbian Christians⁷⁵. Possibly, the Ft. Ancient culture was the Welsh Indians⁷⁶. But what about during that Megalithic and Transition Period? What was the status of pyramid building in Kentucky? If the Cosmic Mountain archetype is to be maintained, shouldn't it be also here in Kentucky?

Indeed, it was, but not in the form that we've seen elsewhere, in stone, and in perfect geometric shape. Rather, it was more similar to Poverty Point⁷⁷: an ode to the Jupiter and Venus events, which came to then later define the Hopewell culture so thoroughly⁷⁸. While the Adena maintained the religion of the Sun God (Saturn)⁷⁹, the Hopewell seem to have focused upon the **Thunder**⁸⁰ God (Jupiter), and to have also revered the events of the Great Comet Venus, as she left the Saturnian system and went screaming through the solar system like a brave warrior (see: Athena). At Great Serpent Mound they recorded the bow shock, and at Spratt Site, too, they made a perfect replica. The plasma tails and bow shocks for these features of Venus have been found, scientifically, but imagine the power of seeing it firsthand!

Throughout North America over 30 giant serpent mounds were built - by hand, as the Cherokee have recorded⁸¹ - and they did so in appeasement to the glory of Uktena, the Great Serpent. But it did not

⁷¹ "Giza Power Plant," and "Lost Technologies of Ancient Egypt," by Chris Dunn

⁷² <https://phys.org/news/2018-07-reveals-great-pyramid-giza-focus.html>

⁷³ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211285517307267>

⁷⁴ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final

⁷⁵

https://www.academia.edu/38592435/Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_Addendum_Implications_for_Diffusionist_arch_for_pre-Columbian_Christians

⁷⁶

<https://sites.google.com/site/electricuniversegateway/home/research-papers/uchellthehighlordandshangdisfrcareaga>

⁷⁷ Which conforms both to the Athena/Venus Shell motif *and* the carbon dating matches the 1600 BC Velikovskian dating for the Exodus Event.

⁷⁸ The author is currently conducting research to demonstrate the connection of the Chillicothe and Newark octagons and the Jovian North Pole.

⁷⁹ Remember: Mt. Horeb and similar c-henge mounds from Indiana and the British Isles show coherence with the Cosmic Pole and Sun God motif, whereby the crater rim discharge 'bridge' enables the shaman to enter the center of the area and to make sacrifices to appease the Midnight Sun/Best Sun/Superior Sun (Shamash in Sumer, Ra in Egypt). The mound is then maintained by hand, in reverence, until apparently ~ 500 AD when the last major electro comet rips across the northern hemisphere towards Bolivia. This causes widespread disease and leads to a change in mound pyramid type, with a split in North America between two rival cultures: the Mississippians with their step pyramid types, and the Ft. Ancients with their conical type.

⁸⁰ In coelbren the Th rune is the Secret Name for God, /|\\, IAU or IAO

⁸¹ "Myths of the Cherokee," by James Mooney

matter: the destructions came anyhow, and the end of Egypt was the fury of the Thunderbirds⁸² in North America, too. The Great Bird brought thunderous destruction in the land⁸³, not the least of which right here in the bluegrass.

Already we have found the lichtenburg formations of the knobs, and the Thunderbolt strike site at Big Sink (Versailles), which is a mile wide.⁸⁴ What else do we find?

Studying the runes from various Welsh sites, and other rock art sites, I have found evidence of excellent astronomic study here in Kentucky. Take for example, this remnant of an observation of Saturn's South pole, with Mars in front⁸⁵.

Big Turtle Rockshelter glyph; Coy et al...

How do we know it was Saturn? How did the Egyptians know? In my studies of the Ramesses II stele, I found that the Egyptians satisfied the measurement ratios of the diameters of both Saturn and Jupiter to within < 1% of the satellite measurements⁸⁶:

$$\frac{\text{polar diameter}}{\text{equatorial diameter}} < 1\% \text{ of satellite measurement}$$

But what about these step pyramids versus the conical pyramids? I can think of only three reasons why the difference mattered. First, it would seem that the Giants (Padoucans as the Cherokee and others recorded them), preferred the conical type, and occupied the regions of the state, and the Falls of the Ohio, that overlaps the Ft. Ancient mounds and the Welsh runes. This more or less defines the relative region where we find their influence.⁸⁷ But their flourishing does appear to be over by about 1250-1300 AD. Whereas, the Mississippians, as recorded by the Cherokee **and** the Chinese⁸⁸, were a race of priestly and feudal cultures which inhabited the western part of the state till the 1400s, and below the Falls of the

⁸² Isn't it interesting that the word for thunderstrike in Chinese means thunder-bird?

⁸³ The spear of Odin (Jupiter) is gugnir, and it means "to shake"; in Chinese Zhen/Shock literally means earth trembling.

⁸⁴ See the author's September 2017 presentation at AKHA:

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1F1UtMW-J7_GUybY58355xWOLQ3DLjdnkcOMXAall1xM/edit?usp=sharing

⁸⁵ "Rock Art of Kentucky," Fuller et al...

⁸⁶ https://www.academia.edu/38492475/The_Solar_Orb_in_Egypt

⁸⁷ <http://bit.ly/214y1wQ>

⁸⁸ "To the Gates of Fengtu," by L.B. Nickless

Ohio, and generally surrounded both west and south, the Archaic pyramids. Why did they do so? Possibly they preferred to stay near to but off of, the archaic pyramids, some of which were ancient by Egyptian standards, being from 7000 BC - 3000 BC or 5000 BC - 1500 BC in age. They are large, but single platform, being anywhere from 60 - 350 feet in length and width, and from 4 - 16 feet in height and made of mostly shells and bones⁸⁹. This is very different from the dirt platform mounds of the Mississippians, which sometimes had 2 or 3 steps, and were shaped geometrically (on purpose), and definitely date to the Christian era. Perhaps the mysterious origins of these people were known very well to the Mississippians, who had perhaps originated from Toltec, Mayan, or Aztec lands, but intermingled with local tribes. Perhaps this is where their caste system comes from, again recorded as both by the Cherokee and the Chinese. We do know from the Cherokee that they had a great war to punish the Cahokian peoples for their arrogance. In Spanish history we know that there was great anger with the Mexica (Aztecs) for slave-war-scourging and bloody sacrifices **atop** pyramids, and the Spanish had important aid from various Nahuatl tribes that paid bloody tribute to the Mexica. Perhaps here the Welsh aided the Cherokee, and were destroyed for it, and fleeing certain annihilation a contingent went North to become the Mandans⁹⁰, and the rest went southeast and mingled with Creek, Choctaw, and Cherokee to escape⁹¹. Did they make their last stands at Stone Fort and Indian Fort?

Map of various culture sites of the Great River Valley; credit: author

⁸⁹ Which is very marvelous either in patience or logistics. The time it took to make these platform mounds is really mind-boggling.

⁹⁰ "Footprints of the Welsh Indians," by Dr. Traxel.

⁹¹ Hence the mysterious origins of the Melungeons

Rayburn Johnson Site

SKETCH MAP OF SITE

Include north arrow and scale. Attach xerox section of U.S.G.S. quad map

15Bt41 is an Archaic mound site which shares much in common with other middens, but has a fort-like arrangement.⁹² River is about 380' in elevation⁹³

⁹² The following scans are all credit of the Office of State Archaeology which was gracious enough to give me copies

⁹³ <http://www.uky.edu/KGS/water/library/gwatlas/Butler/Topography.htm>

15Bt6 -Deweese Mound has a farm on top of it, it is so large!

15Bt5 - Carlston Annis Mound; you may recognize this one from the Facebook group cover. Although much reduced in size, it nevertheless is dominant over the bend in the river, and may have been strategically placed.

Map of the Read Site from Rolingsson 1967, page 51 (reduced).

Sometimes the sites are all heavily spaced out.

15 Oh19 - Jimtown Hill; the dimensions of this Archaic platform are huge: 110m x 35m (361' x 115')

Or was it instead a matter of commerce, as per Rick Osman's intimations⁹⁴. Important trade empires dealing in copper, mica, pearls, furs, fluorite, iron, etc. and for the Falls of the Ohio and similar stone fortresses perhaps a great war was waged for territorial control? Later, it would have been simply an accident that the Chinese brought the smallpox and mayhaps this, rather than Cherokee wrath, ended the Cahokians?

Or was it more of the growing cultural clash between the Ft. Ancients (as descendents possibly of the Hopewell and Welsh mixture), and their more pure worship of the gods, and the "unsacred" and bloody sun worship of the Cahokians; not only using different pyramids, but forming stockades and engaging in slavery and angering the Lakota nations? Or did Algonquins, Siouans, and Iroquoians get together to engage in an American Indian alliance⁹⁵ to destroy the white skinned Ft. Ancients and thence afterwards finished off the Cahokians who had been weakened by Chinese smallpox, drought, and flood? Was the use of the wheel forbidden, and the Cahokians violated this for farming? Did the proposed American Indian coalition wipe out nearly all traces of Welsh and Mississippian runic writing they could find, leaving only the Gaitskill tablet and other runes such as have been found? What was this mythic war really about? Perhaps the cultural clash was a mask for secret political and economic motivations... or was it self-defense against growing political and economic influence in Kithiki/Kentucky, where all were supposed to be able to hunt?

All of these have possibilities, and I can't help but feel we are circling nearer to the truth. But the heart of the mystery appears to be the cultural difference of opinion - be it geopolitical, cultural, ethnic, or sociogenetic - between the three mysterious groups: the Mississippian-Cahokians, the Ft. Ancient/Hopewellians and the hunter-gatherer American Indians.

Was this a tripartite war? Who were the allies? Was it a "Romances of the Three Kingdoms" type situation, or was literally every tribe its own nation? What was the role of the trade partners in Carolina, Michigan, the southwest, and even South America? Who was the priest class that abused their power, and were they in league or paying tribute to the Aztecs or Mayans? When we can answer these questions, then the meaning of "dark and bloody ground" will finally become absolutely clear!

⁹⁴ see "Graves of the Golden Bear" and Rick's series in Ancient American.

⁹⁵ As intimated in the famous prophecy of Tenskwatawa

Amazonia-Kentucky Connection?

By Sf. Ramon Careaga

In the previous article I mentioned the presence of **huge** mounds in the formation of shell middens of single platforms, constructed in the era of pyramid building worldwide. I proposed that there was some form of logistical plan, and that it is very unlikely that subsistence aboriginal cultures employed garbage dumping. Rather, it is my belief that these mounds⁹⁶ were planned.

Since then, I have learned through Graham Hancock's new book, "America Before," about the Amazonian Dark Earth soil called terra-preta⁹⁷. In short, this soil was not only manufactured⁹⁸, it is incredibly proficient at fertilizing agricultural forests⁹⁹. With it, the Amazonians were able to ostensibly feed *millions* of people¹⁰⁰, just as reported by the Spanish conquistadors in their deep jungle searches for lost golden cities¹⁰¹. The Archaic Kentuckians also preferred tree products.¹⁰² Whereas before the mainstream archaeology was self-assured that no more than few thousands¹⁰³ - and no practical civilization¹⁰⁴ - could have existed in the Amazon, we now know due to the earthworks¹⁰⁵ found in and around *Llanos de Moxos (Mojos)*¹⁰⁶, Bolivia, near to both Brazil and Peru, and not very far from Lake Titicaca.

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<https://heritage.ky.gov/Documents/TheArchaeologyofKYAnUpdateVol1.pdf?fbclid=IwAR0pTm0vl7nYeJIMYmVHYIsnyz2LPOKLHtNL9pySNh6NsBp1707Xsik5DiA>

⁹⁷ "Terra preta owes its characteristic black color to its weathered charcoal content,[2] and was made by adding a mixture of charcoal, bone, broken pottery, compost and manure to the otherwise relatively infertile Amazonian soil. A product of indigenous soil management and slash-and-char agriculture,[3] the charcoal is stable and remains in the soil for thousands of years, binding and retaining minerals and nutrients.[4][5]

Terra preta is characterized by the presence of low-temperature charcoal residues in high concentrations:[2] of high quantities of tiny pottery shards; of organic matter such as plant residues, animal feces, fish and animal bones, and other material; and of nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, calcium, zinc and manganese.[6] Fertile soils such as terra preta show high levels of microorganic activities and other specific characteristics within particular ecosystems."

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Terra_preta

⁹⁸ <http://bit.ly/2V0S1Dp>

⁹⁹ <http://bit.ly/2lWfsvW>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.penn.museum/sites/expedition/hidden-earthworks-in-the-forests-of-the-bolivian-amazon/>

¹⁰¹ <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/archaeology-and-history/archaeology/seven-cities-of-cibola/>

¹⁰² "The inhabitants of the Ohio Valley were complex hunter-gatherer societies who relied on food rich resources of the deciduous forest and floodplain, including both marine and terrestrial animals and plants. A constant crop of hickory nuts, acorns, roots, and seeds were utilized by the foragers of the area, as well as later domestication of squash in the Green River Region reveals an evident trend toward subsistence agriculture, though this has not been confirmed at Indian Knoll."

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Indian_Knoll

¹⁰³ <https://www.sas.upenn.edu/~cerickso/baures/baures2.htm>

¹⁰⁴ <http://bit.ly/2H27vmU>

¹⁰⁵ <http://bit.ly/2vM17Kd>

¹⁰⁶ https://www.jstor.org/stable/40991767?seq=1#page_scan_tab_contents

This is quite the reversal of the mainstream situation, and it should all by itself as a fact cause almost all faith in neo-Victorian uniformitarian archaeology to be lost, or at the very minimum, critically examined.

Nevertheless, the ADE's are all highly specialized technologies. Why is this of interest? In the mainstream they are maintaining that these soils were accidentally discovered¹⁰⁷. However, when I heard the ingredients¹⁰⁸ of the ADE's I immediately recognized the composition of materials¹⁰⁹, and indeed recognized the M.O. (as it were) of the 'rummage heaps' in the Amazon:

- Shells
- Bones
- Ceramic pieces
- Animal parts
- Human carcasses in disarray non ceremonial burials
- Arrowheads
- Signs of fire and black layers (carbon)

¹⁰⁷ "Soils with elevated charcoal content and a common presence of pottery remains can accrete accidentally near living quarters as residues from food preparation, cooking fires, animal and fish bones, broken pottery, etc., accumulated. Many terra preta soil structures are now thought to have formed under kitchen middens, as well as being manufactured intentionally on larger scales.^[14] Farmed areas around living areas are referred to as terra mulata. Terra mulata soils are more fertile than surrounding soils but less fertile than terra preta, and were most likely intentionally improved using charcoal." (Wiki)

¹⁰⁸ "In the international soil classification system World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB) Terra preta is called Pretic Anthrosol. The most common original soil before transformed into a terra preta is the Ferralsol. Terra preta has a carbon content ranging from high to very high (more than 13–14% organic matter) in its A horizon, but without hydromorphic characteristics.^[25] Terra preta presents important variants. For instance, gardens close to dwellings received more nutrients than fields farther away.^[26] The variations in Amazonian dark earths prevent clearly determining whether all of them were intentionally created for soil improvement or whether the lightest variants are a by-product of habitation. Terra preta's capacity to increase its own volume—thus to sequester more carbon—was first documented by [pedologist](#) William I. Woods of the University of Kansas.^[13] This remains the central mystery of terra preta.

The processes responsible for the formation of terra preta soils are:^[1]

- Incorporation of wood charcoal
- Incorporation of organic matter and of nutrients
- Growth of microorganisms and animals in the soil" (Wiki)

¹⁰⁹ <http://bit.ly/2H2jP6l>

“Location of Amazonian Dark Earth sites (blue dots) and the study area of the analyses. Black areas are regions masked from inclusion in our analysis due low biomass or non-forested areas.”; credit: Palace, McMichael, et al.. (Ibid.)

Apparently, when these refuse are layered correctly, the carbon sequesters and locks away nutrients for centuries¹¹⁰, increasing the soil’s production via a unique presence of perfect biomes and micro-organisms¹¹¹.

Without any dancing around the subject, this is precisely the ingredients list of Archaic Shell Middens, the most enigmatic of which are in the Green River district¹¹², but which appear all along the Gulf and East coast and up the southern river systems.¹¹³

Now, the plot actually thickens, as the North America middens actually are much, much older than the Amazonian middens, which date to the equal Adena and/or Middle Woodland Period¹¹⁴. There is some evidence that they were designed and in use for many thousands of years¹¹⁵, but all in all, they were from the Adena to the Historic/Inca period¹¹⁶. Whereas the Kithiki mounds are from the Archaic and Early Woodland period, 7,000 YBP - 1800 YBP.

It has also been an important mystery to discover *where* the Archaic Kentuckians went. It may appear, possibly, that they left and *diffused* to South America, perhaps returning home, as South America is well known to have older carbon dated settlements than North America, generally (at least 16,000

¹¹⁰ <http://bit.ly/2Jfn8Ja>

¹¹¹ <http://bit.ly/2VOaWFK>

¹¹² <http://bit.ly/2IYq39J>

¹¹³ <http://bit.ly/2Y2bMfy>

¹¹⁴ 500 BC - 500 AD http://www.ohiohistorycentral.org/w/Middle_Woodland_Period vs 450 BCE origin for terra preta

¹¹⁵ <http://bit.ly/2Jg2w3j>

¹¹⁶ As late as 1500 AD <https://go.nature.com/2Y0s4ps>

YBP). While this wouldn't be considered impossible by the mainstream Clovis First archaeologists, I am unsure there is any evidence of their civilizing any of Mexico in between, or any of Latin America. Furthermore, the penetration to the heart of South America seems to indicate an Amazon River vector. Now, if they were a river folk, used to the navigation of streams in search of shell resources, it could easily make sense that they would use the coasts and avoid the mountains or penetration with the Nahuatl tribes of Mexico, and instead continued past the Andes east until finding the origins of the Amazon¹¹⁷. They may have been hindered from settling the downstream portions, or maybe preferred waters that had different fish, as the Amazon is well known for many dangerous fish and serpents. This may have encouraged them to look for climates similar to Kentucky's sub-tropical to temperate climates, higher up in the mountains, but near to lots of plains. Llanos de Moxos is perfect for agriculture *if* you have a technique to deal with unideal soils.

(Left: Hopeton Earthworks, Squier & Davis) (Right: Amazon Earthworks)

Could the permaculturalists of the Amazon have come from Kentucky, and were the Archaic Shell 'pyramid' mounds of midwestern Kentucky, mostly of the Green River Valley related to the creation of dark earth soils? At this point I'd like to ask people to help me connect with a soil scientist or open-minded archaeologist and present this evidence to them. Maybe instead of calling these garbage middens we can finally ascribe some type of genius to what may be the progenitors of the Allegewi (Adena-Hopewell) and inspirers of the potentially Nahuatlesque¹¹⁸ Mississippian cultures. As you will recall I showed there was a tendency to avoid Archaic lands for creating pyramid platform mounds.

¹¹⁷ "Spatiotemporal patterns of pre-Columbian people in Amazonia," McMichael & Bush, Quaternary Research, 2019

¹¹⁸ See Mooney's "Myths of the Cherokee" for descriptions of the mound people culture and [why they were wiped out](https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/index.htm). <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/index.htm> According to the Chinese, the Cahokians engaged in sacrifice and torture, which matches the Cherokee descriptions, as well as Spanish accounts of the Nahuatls such as the powerful Mexica (Aztecs).

Perhaps there were specific reasons why? Could this also link two empires temporo-spatially, and explain the similarity of Hopewell and Amazonia mounds of the same period (late Woodland)?

Earthworks of the SRA

- | | | | |
|-------------------------|-------------------------|-----------------------|--|
| Ditched enclosures | | Mounds | |
| ● Ceremonial centres | ● Mounded ring villages | ● Other sites | |
| ○ Fortified settlements | ○ Large platform mounds | ■ Tropical rainforest | |

“Distribution of earthworks in the SRA and other sites in the Amazon^{68,69}. ..., UTB survey area in the Upper Tapajós Basin (the area delimited by the red box is shown in detail in Fig. 4). Scale bar = 1000 km” credit: Nature (deSouza et al.)

Amazonian Octagon Earthworks. Compare with my work on Ohio Earthworks: <http://bit.ly/2vBjLUZ>

Update on the Webb Museum

By Sf. Ramon Careaga

On Friday, July 12th, I spoke with Mark Kornbluh, Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences, and his associate Dean about the status of the renovations of the University of Kentucky's Anthropology department. To date they've made six hirings, including a new GIS curator, an artifacts curator, and a specialist in the region's archaeology.

Dean Kornbluh re-assured me that their goal is both enhancement and proper organization of Kentucky's amazing, priceless, irreplaceable collection, as well as enhancing educational outreach. They aren't yet sure how to do that, except to enhance the research area, and establish a clear protocol on how to provide access to trustworthy public researchers and archaeologists. However, there will be discussions over the next few weeks and months as to how that protocol will be implemented, to vet individuals and also receive feedback from even the Independent Research community at large.

It is my opinion that this is absolutely needed. As curator of the Hidden Kentucky project, I can say that there is almost no proper public education outreach for Kentucky's rare cultural past. We know more, at this point, about the Mayans than we do about the Allegewi people (Adena/Hopewell), or the Ft. Ancient peoples. While Wickliffe State Historic Site offers a small educational experience, it is on the Mississippi river edge and far away from the vast majority of Kentuckians. Many Kentuckians still feel a close kinship to Shawnee and Cherokee ancestors, and moreover the knowledge of the experience of pioneers, both historic and pre-Columbian, has been buried or lost, inappropriately. The era of Indiana-Jones style archaeology has come to an end, thankfully due to NAGPRA. But the downside has been just outright hiding of important history and artifacts. While the state and public Universities must comply with Federal Law and protect sites, artifacts, rock art, mummies, etc., it is also their job to educate the Commonwealth as a commonwealth is common ownership by all citizens. I want to say first and foremost I am incredibly optimistic about this change. The addition of proper heating and cooling facilities, of cataloging and protocols for handling, and enhanced security (much of which has already been implemented since the building was closed May 28th) is all steps in the right direction.

I even informed Dean Kornbluh of our knowledge of the whereabouts of Fawn Hoof (mummified remains held at the Smithsonian), and made a note that there may come a time when all the displays and protections are in place, to bring her home. It was a fantastic conversation which included a great and generous gesture to invite the AKHA leaders to come and discuss our concerns and desires for the state's priceless historical collection and the general direction of archaeology.

Let me add also that there is a way to utilize the collection for educational tourism, such as how Ohio or Illinois has done, which is tasteful, respectful, and helpful. I do hope we can even make inroads towards a proper Allegewi Museum one day here in the heart of the Bluegrass, and also dispel nonsensical proto-Victorian views such as how the Mississippians

wore loincloths, etc. (now that the Chinese texts have told us distinctly how they were dressed). If we can learn anything from the bad direction West Virginia has taken at its own famous sites, in hiding past research, it's that you don't have to throw the baby out with the bath water. It isn't racist to have inquest into Kentucky history, as it appears diverse (according to Cherokee Myths!) as well as unique, rich, and while bloody, also beautiful. We can stamp out the racism of Victorian pseudoscientific archaeology while also learning from the Native tribes how they prefer to be remembered, seen, and respected.

Dog's Laughter Falls trip Report

OK, actually, its name is Dog Slaughter Falls... isn't that terrible?! So I changed it to Dog's Laughter Falls to protect the innocent and reflect the true feeling. The kids and I took off for this gem of a waterfall hidden away between Corbin and the Cumberland Falls State Resort Park on 8/27/22. It took one hour & forty minutes from Lexington but was well worth it for a cool down. This waterfall is **cold**, but comes equipped with two pools to swim in, a sandy beach to lay a towel on and just lie out. The sun streams in through a jungly, but high canopy. Other than the occasional deer or horsefly, you feel completely nestled away. Streams of happy travelers come by - and yet far less trash to clean up than at Flat Lick Falls! - and you can talk to them. They are always happy because when they see the falls and breathe in the negative ions their stresses melt away. Laughter can be heard all around as people nervously dip, or bravely jump in. The falls are not super tall.

Actually, DSF is a class V rapid, one of only two in Kentucky, and the curtain that comes down is just powerful enough to beat you like a rough massage. The pool is full of creatures that tickle and nibble, and little fish are everywhere in both pools. Green covered sandstone rocks, and wild Yucatan like boulders with vines and ferns are round about you. Fir and pine as well as Ash and Tulip tower overhead. But the scene is dominated by a cliff overhang that guarantees a cool experience. This waterfall is best on 90+ degree days, but we went it was 86 F and the 1 mile hike in (from the better trailhead, at the Kayak putin, not the Google Maps!) is not that hard at all. Moderately difficult for seniors,

mild for everyone else. We listened to “The Electric Universe” by David Bodanis, on audible.

Overall this waterfall ranks high in Kentucky’s list of waterfalls. I think it was around #7 in my upcoming book. But in terms of unforgettable experiences, it’s second to none. It is so cold it can reduce 100 degree weather to a Fall pleasantry.

Unfortunately you do have to hike back out. But at least you will sweat out the cold water! Also, you feel spiritually much cleaner. Kids will enjoy the beachy area, and right now a nice ash tree log has recently fallen over providing a good place to sit to put your shoes back on (carry sandals etc. in your backpack, and bring plenty of water and snacks!). By the way, you can get there from the SRP if you choose to stay at the lodge. And if you really want to, you can also go swim in Eagle Falls on the other side of the bridge at the Cumberland Falls! It’s a very different character from DSF, but still worthy of a ¾ mile hike. I’d rate Dog’s Laughter Falls a 9.3/10 though, factoring in the travel time and hike. The cold makes it really limited compared to Flat Lick or Silver Creek or Eagle Falls, but it is definitely something to put on your

bucket list. 100% will do again, and again.

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